

Implementation of Universal Education Theory in global education system towards the development of individual, teams, society and prevention of corruption

Author: Rejaul Abedin, PhD, FCMAN

Abstract:

The moral value is significant for everyone in every sphere of human life. Moral lessons should be properly taught among students in Schools, Colleges, Universities, Vocational training centers, Madrasas and so on. Above all, along with parents or guardians, it is the prime duty and responsibility of the educator to impart moral based values in order to develop moral qualities such as humility, integrity, truthfulness, courtesy, tolerance, sacrifice, mutual compromise etc. among the youth and all level pupils. It will assist in developing positive, constructive social attitudes in new generation which prompt them to raise their moral voice against social evils. The harmonious coexistence of diverse ideologies in society requires respect for ethical and moral values. Value addition from moral education inculcates these virtues in a systematic and widely acceptable manner. Morality is basically the knowledge of knowing what is right and what is wrong. With the morality human being can preserve their sense of humanity and empathy for others' sorrows while at the same time people can retain their sense of unselfishness for others. Here in this research paper, the "Universal Education Theory" is explained and elaborated which innovated on 2019 A.D. by Dr. Rejaul Abedin, PhD, FCMAN. The innovator who strongly believes that in the present world Universal Education Theory will

IJOBAS

Accepted 01 August 2019

Published 03 August 2019

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3360442

be useful as it will redirect to gain moral education or to train individual through morally during their academic, social and unearthy life. Moreover, Moral education can control human mind to prevent corruption, manipulation at both the micro and macro levels.

Keywords: Universal Education Theory, Moral Education, Universal Education Formula, Prevention of corruption, UE formula,

About Author

Author1, (Corresponding Author) Designation: Adjunct Faculty, Organization: Asian European University (AEU), Location: London, Country: UK

Accounting and Finance Department, North East University Bangladesh (NEUB),
Consultant Head, CEO & Founder at www.twcmsi.org

I. Introduction: Universal Education Theory (UE), a distinctive philosophical approach that seeks to repair or amend all the evils from individual character through learning appropriate moral education in their personal and academic life. This theory also encourages developing value for human being as this leads benefits through Value Addition throughout Training and Development for Individuals, attending students in academic programs, participating trainees or pupils in the different moral programs and self-learning also can be useful for moral development. This “UE” formula also strongly believes that if it applies towards the moral development of teams and individual trainee then along with individual and team overall a society can be benefited from it.

Universal Education Theory/Formula:

$$UE = [H_V + (E_A + E_{ST}) + M_R] - I_e$$

Where, UE = Universal Education.

H_V = Human being as an Individual who requires Value addition.

E_A = Education from Academic sources.

E_{ST} = Education from Self Learning and Talent from Almighty Allah (SWT).

M_R = Morality / Moral Education from Religion.

I_e = Eradication of all Evils from individual character (Individual Evils)/ Eradicating the evils of corruption.

II. Objective of the research:

The significance of “Universal Education Theory” for grooming up morality through education -

Universal Education Theory (UE) is ensured by a theory or formula system of learning morality or ethics or moral education from any religion. As it is proved that all religion heavenly tells human being, do the right things avoid wrong or unethical ones.

As a result of the implementation of Universal Education Theory (UE) in academic stages, the possible significance may outcomes which mentioned below:

- Removes egoism, Lust, Anger, greed, pride, Attachment, Covetousness from individual and group life.
- Reduces biases, nepotism, corruption and violence.
- Develops value to the human personality.
- Promotes ethical sense of human beings.
- Expands human power, goodness, and principles.
- Eradicates ignorance and enlighten all countries and nations.

III. Methodology of the research: In this research, Secondary data and descriptive method and resources used.

A. Scope and areas of “Universal Education Theory (UE)”

There are huge scope and numerous areas available where Universal Education Theory can be utilized, the few of them are mentioned as follows:

- Primary School level.
- High Secondary School level.
- College level (11 and 12 classes).
- University (Undergraduate level / Degree level).
- University (Post graduate level / Master level).
- Vocational training stages.

Universal Education Theory (UE), that prepares young and adult pupils for life, the workforce and the society and that aims to reduce injustice, discrimination, extremism, gender, social class, racism & ethnicity in every phases of life, encourage to practice morality in political life, social life, and promote individual learning through ethically and to develop inner mind & students able to show respect to the other community people and religions and so on.

B. Benefits of Value Addition through Training and Development for Individuals and Teams, and Society

We all know that value addition via academic and other sources is an individual thing. Making an individual progress relies on a whole range of influencing factors and students or learners make progress at different times of their life and at different rates.

Here the concept of "Value addition" actually indicates where the individual quality enhancement made by a person or group of people to any area required by the concerned individual(s) in order to exchange these quality and good deeds with others through money or without any exchange value.

Individual values: Individual values reflect how a person show up in his or her life and their specific needs-the principles s/he live by and what they consider important for their self-interest. Individual values include: enthusiasm, creativity, humility and personal fulfillment.

Value addition to develop personal value can be made through many ways as for example, it could include:

- Participation in the In-house training
- Participation in the academic programs
- Participation in the religious moral education
- Attending in the On-the-job learning (In terms of employee)
- Mentoring Advice on specific area
- Individual study or self-learning using online or offline study materials
- Eradication of all Evils from individual character (Individual Evils)

C. Education from Academic Sources

- "Academic Education" is generally defined as education which has learning as its primary purpose. Several institutions and educational systems have equated academic with "University " but this is not always the case.

- The intend of higher academic studies should be to build a capacity to adapt and apply a "foundation knowledge", so that a course graduate is well placed to progress successfully during their lifespan, both in their private life and working life.
- This clearly differs from Vocational education that has a primary focus on "preparing to perform in a workplace"; or "life education" which may have a purpose of preparing to live better.

D. What's self-learning and Self-directed learning strategies?

Self-learning is an emerging form of learning that has emerged due to the availability of learning resources online and offline in both ways. Self-learning enables learner to learn what learner want when they want, and how they want. Learner drive the learning process and this tends to be more effective that instructional learning.

Self-learning is the modern form of learning. Not that it has replaced traditional, instructional learning, but it has supplemented it and with some great results. Self-oriented learning has been proven to be effective, convenient, and fast, to the rise of the internet. Nowadays, learned can learn how to do almost anything through a simple Google search or by watching a YouTube tutorial, and by simply reading printed materials. Self-learning is the new form of learning that is equipping individual with skills that are relevant to their daily activities. However, this can be a challenging form of learning even for the brightest students, since it requires lots of discipline.

Self-learning gives learner the ability to identify problems and quickly look for effective solutions on their own. This could be from colleagues, the internet or by exploration. Whatever the case, challenges and obstacles do not kill learner drive to get things done, instead, they provide learner with new opportunities to learn something new at their own pace and time. Learners get to learn how to actively look for solutions instead of having solutions brought to them. Besides, learner can easily adapt to changes in the environment due to the ability to learn fast.

Self-learning can be quite valuable for those who do not have the enough spare time or age to enroll in formal courses and degrees as well as for those actually who cannot travel to a specific location to educate themselves.

On the other hand, self-learning is neither location constrained nor time bound, it is self-paced, and all that is needed is an access to a computer and an internet connection to engage in self-learning. This means that for both students and working professionals and just about everyone, has the valuable opportunities to enrich their knowledge and to enhance their skills.

E. Benefits of Training for Individuals and Teams

The training activities have a positive impact on the performance of individuals and teams. Training activities can also be useful regarding other outcomes at both the individual and team level (e.g., motivation, attitudes, and empowerment).

F. Benefits of Training for Society

Mostly, economists have conducted the research on the relationship between training activities and their benefits for society; the focal dependent variable is national economic performance. Overall, this body of literature leads to the ending that training efforts produce improvements in the quality of the labor force or individual, which in turn is one of the most important contributors to national economic growth (e.g., Becker 1962, 1964). The Economists coined the terms “human capital” and “capital formation in people” in referring mainly to schooling and on-the-job training (Wang et al. 2002).

G. Benefits related to organizational performance

Several studies in European countries have conducted and documented the impact of training on organizational performance. Aragon-Sánchez et al. (2003) investigated the relationship between training and organizational performance by distributing a survey to 457 small and medium-size businesses in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Finland, Portugal, and Spain. The organizational performance was operationalized as (a) effectiveness (i.e., human resource indicators, employee involvement, and quality), and (b) profitability (i.e., benefits before interest and taxes, sales volume, and a ratio of benefit before taxes/sales). The results indicated that some types of training activities, including on-the-job training and training inside the organization using in-house trainers, were positively related to most dimensions of effectiveness and profitability.

H. Benefits of Training for Organizations

The overall picture changes among companies recognized for their employee’s commitment to training. Fewer than 5% of all training programs are assessed in terms of their financial benefits to the organization (Swanson 2001).

I. Other Benefits

Other research demonstrates that the impact of training on outcomes other than job performance or on variables that serve as antecedents to job performance.

J. Morality / Moral Education from Religion

The word *moral* derives from a Latin root (*mos, moris*) and means the code or customs of a people, the social glue that defines how individuals should live together. The Moral Education program covers four pillars – character and morality; the individual and the community; civic studies; and cultural studies and blends academic content with an exploration of character and ethics. Usually, it has been shown that as a progressive series of units to be taught over twelve years of schooling from Grade 1 to Grade 12.

K. Objectives of Moral Education

Moral education refers to helping children and adult learners acquire those virtues or moral habits that will help out them individually led good life and live peacefully and at the same time become productive, contributing members of their societies or communities. In this vision, moral education should contribute not only to the students as individuals, but also to the social cohesion of a community.

The ultimate outcome of Moral Education is to create a generation of citizens who:

- Build Individual Character
- Instill Ethical outlook
- Foster Community
- Endear Culture
- Develop Society

L. Eradication of All Evils from Individual Characters

Individual Evils: Evil is a powerful force that some people believe to exist, and which causes wicked and bad things to happen in any phases in the world. If anyone refers to an evil, it means a very unpleasant or harmful situation or activity. If describe someone (individual) as evil, then it mean that they are very wicked by nature and take pleasure in doing things that harm other people anyway either directly or indirectly.

M. What is good and evil or bad? How can we distinguish it?

There are several instances that when an event occurs the effect is seen to be positive on one individual while the same has a negative effect on the other. It is difficult to really understand as what is good and what is evil or bad either. In fact, if someone feel they are the two sides of the same coin, where the side of the coin that we see is taken as an understanding with respect to an event, law, culture or in general every aspect whether materialistic, abstract, spiritual, etc. that form our life and world while the other side is either totally ignored or remains unobserved.

Generally, the activity of someone's will show us the distinguish area whether someone doing the evil/wrong tasks or good deeds!

So, here is the scope of implementing the "Universal Education Theory/Formula" as individual(s) sometimes doing the wrong things or showing the evil performance in their day to day social life.

N. Results and Findings of the Study

Human being all are not by born meritorious, intellectual and moral. Though, there a lot religious school, colleges and Madrasas located around the Globe but all the people generally not keenly interested to study in religious educational institutions. Hence, here is a scope or gap to include moral educational subjects in schools, colleges, Universities, Vocational training centers respectively. So, they require UE (Universal education theory) to follow

which may aid to minimize or eliminate possible harms by preventing or removing from one's individual character and may help to maximize or promote one's ethical strength and standard in order to lead his or her (believers) life in both the area in here (present life) or hereafter (life after death).

In most of the academic education, it is found that, religious education or moral education is almost missing so, human being don't have possibility to be learned by morally or ethically. Moral education teaches people to be trained in ethically sound in their life in the side like conscience, psychologically and spiritually. Why moral education or training it is mainly a reason, it directs human towards all good deeds except bad deeds or corrupt intention or harm others. Generally, people don't embezzle or snatch other's asset or corruption of other's wealth but if they don't trained morally then situation may arise such as in the absence of land lords or owners they may be deceived or weak people may be faced by injustice during his/her trial issue. Syndicated businessmen's unethically may involve with price hike of the products and services but due to practice of the UE (Universal education theory) such unethical malpractices will be eliminated.

Before proper academic or moral education as an individual may have chance to be captured some evil habits, unwanted knowledge, wicked skills, bad attitudes, criminal behavior, deceitful tendency and devils character etc. from his bad companions or from societies. But these situations and status should be altered by the application of moral values of education from religion. When such evils individual characterizes be able to eradicated from one's self life then Universal Education theory or formula could be seen its effectiveness. Universal education means, the opportunity for all people to have equal prospect in education or training, regardless of their social status, gender, race, ethnicity background or physical and mental disabilities. If an individual to get appropriate education or training then s/he can be able to develop their economy, society, nation, country all consequently. S/he will not involve any unethical activity like financial or economical corruption, manipulation; so far biases, nepotism, greediness attitude shall not be raised. As a result of Universal Education, it develops personal qualities of mercy, generosity, kindness, and charity. It is also assisted to enrich one's tendency for humanity, self-sacrifice, love, and promote high moral ideals of action for the sack of good for others. Moral excellence actually comes from practice of religious study along with academic learning.

Ordinary morality doesn't welcome in UE (Universal education) theory! As for example, a rich individual may perform hajj but later if s/he practices bribery activities or biases against the truth then it is proving that actual moral education is absent here because s/he didn't morally educate. Another example, Doctors should not demand high charge during their consulting hours to patients as this is service oriented not for profit profession for mankind or humanity. Rich businessmen or wealthy people if don't share their Zakat of Ramadan/ Fitrah (An annual tax on Muslims for payment made annually under Islamic law on certain kinds of property and used for charitable and religious obligation purposes) to the needy or poor people's then this is clearly falls under malpractices of moral education.

Human being may be learned from different sources such as academics, self-learning, and talent from God Gifted/ The Allah Almighty (SWT), Moral education from religious studies and so on. Every individual may have unique nature or character but this individual's nature may be consumed some poisonous evil character from their surrounding atmospheres which can be improved by applying the Universal Education theory. It can be strongly assuming that in all levels of education moral education is badly needed. Some people believe that merely this should be included in the school stages but this is not true in a sense, reason is that in an

average all individual are not equally matures in merit or talent. If in the College or University level, they can be able to learn morality in the arena of moral psychology or moral business administration or business morality or morality management then all individual should be able to add moral value from their educators in academic life.

O. Conclusion & Recommendation:

Ethics or morality and values in education have playing pivotal role to develop the students mind in the arena of moral education. The education system should include moral subjects in their curriculum and at least education system itself should not be corrupted, politicized and biased. **(Professor A A M S Arefin Siddique, Former Vice-Chancellor, University of Dhaka, the Daily Star, January 20, 2018)**. Implementation of the “Universal Education Theory” in every country’s education system, then corruption, nepotism, manipulation and violence etc. will be permanently demolished. Last but not the least, it is strongly recommended that there should be at the minimum a single subject based on religion and ethics (moral education) where pupils, participants, irrespective of their religious background, can learn moral teachings of every religion and in respect of every belief system.

References / Sources:

The “Universal Education Theory (UE)” is a unique, individual and scientific researched, innovated theory or formula by Dr. Rejaul Abedin, PhD, FCMAN so, merely few references and sources is given here. But researchers, readers or followers are earnestly advised to read more such moral books strengthening their knowledge, skills, ideas and thoughts on morality or respective field.

- [1] <https://www.thedailystar.net/round-tables/ethics-and-values-education-1522384>, Ethics and Values in Education, The Daily Star, Bangladesh, dated January 20, 2018.
- [2] <http://www.islamiconlineuniversity.com> Moral Foundation of Islamic Culture – IIS 012, Islamic Online University, Source: Course material, IIS 012
- [3] https://www.stltoday.com/pr/news/universal-education-theory-innovated-by-rejaul-abedin-phd/article_5122d122-39e2-11e9-8ae0-5cb9017befd0.html , Universal Education Theory innovated by Rejaul Abedin, PhD, Published at USA news portal, St. Louis Post – Dispatch, dated February 26, 2019
- [4] <https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/views/universal-education-mustering-political-will-to-act-1526314486> , The Financial Express Bangladesh, dated May 14, 2018.
- [5] <https://www.valuescentre.com/mapping-values/values/why-values-are-important>, Why Values Are Important, dated March 20, 2019
- [6] <https://education.stateuniversity.com/pages/2246/Moral-Education.html>, Moral Education, dated March 20, 2019
- [7] <http://www.hermanaguinis.com/Annual09.pdf> , Benefits of Training and Development for Individuals, dated March 9, 2019
- [8] <https://www.brightermonday.co.ke/blog/self-learning/> , Why And How Self-Learning Is Important, dated March 9, 2019

Dr. Rejaul Abedin, PhD, FCMAN is a scholar, researcher and author of renowned books. Earlier he has innovated **Service Quality Models such as EQ SERV, SQ GAPFIL, TQSM**. Currently as an Consulting Head & CEO, Dr. R. Abedin managing his consulting & Training firm “ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International” at Sylhet, Bangladesh and associated in the Accounting & Finance Department in a Private University “North East University Bangladesh (NEUB)”. He can be contacted at E-Mail: jewelrejabd@gmail.com

Cite this article:

Author1, Rejaul Abedin, PhD, FCMAN (2019). Name of the article. *Implementation of Universal Education Theory in global education system towards the development of individual, teams, society and prevention of corruption*, Issue (1), Volume (1), Article (1), 01-11. **DOI:** 10.5281/zenodo.3360442 , Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/current-articles/> , **Issue: 1, Volume: 1, Article: 1, Month: August, Year: 2019.**

https://www.ijarbas.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Implementation-of-Universal-Education-Theory-in-global-education-system-towards-the-development-of-individual-teams-society-and-prevention-of-corruption-Author-Rejaul-Abedin-PhD-FCMAN-IJARBAS.COM_.pdf

Published by

